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Editorial

Letras Raras, an academic journal in the fields of Linguistics and Literature affiliated with the Laboratory for Contemporary Language and Literature Studies (Universidade Federal de Campina Grande), is pleased to present its third regular issue of 2025. This edition features the thematic dossier “*New links in language teaching practices: interfaces between linguistic theory and teaching practice*”, organized by Professors Ana Regina Calindro (Federal University of Rio de Janeiro – UFRJ), Lívia Eccard (State University of Rio de Janeiro – UERJ), and Ana Beatriz Simões (Colégio Pedro II – CP II).

This dossier offers a broad and necessary reflection on the multiple possibilities for articulating theoretical linguistic studies and language teaching practices. The relevance of this discussion lies in the urgent need to rethink and reshape traditional teaching models, creating space for a more critical, integrated, and transformative training of language professionals—whether already in service or still in training.

The contributions in this edition include sixteen original articles by authors affiliated with a range of educational and research institutions, offering a plural and representative panorama of contemporary language teaching practices in diverse contexts. These institutions include: State University of Rio de Janeiro (UERJ), Federal University of Juiz de Fora (UFJF), Federal University of Pampa (Unipampa), Federal University of Amapá (UNIFAP), Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Rio Grande do Sul (IFRS), Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG), Fluminense Federal University (UFF), Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ), State University of Londrina (UEL), University of São Paulo (USP), University Paris 8, Federal University of Santa Maria (UFSM), and Federal University of São Paulo (UNIFESP). This diversity reaffirms the collaborative and interdisciplinary character that defines the spirit of this dossier.

We invite our readers to engage with these pages with openness to dialogue and a receptive ear to the proposals presented. May this reading inspire innovative pedagogical practices and foster

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new connections between academic knowledge and classroom teaching, between the rigor of research and the reality of education.

Enjoy your reading!

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